

Expanding The Scope Of Complementarity As A Principle In International Criminal Law*¹

ABSTRACT

The principle of complementarity in international criminal law presents the idea that states, rather than the International Criminal Court will have priority in proceeding with cases within their jurisdiction. It means that the Court will complement, but not supersede, national jurisdiction. Though this is understandable however, there is need to expand the scope of complementarity in the interest of both national and international criminal justice administration. In the spirit of expansion, the ICC can as often as needed, intervene and assist national courts for some time in prosecuting international crimes. Hence, this article aims at examining the nature and rationale of Complementarity as a Principle in International Criminal Law. The objective is to highlight the need for the expansion of the scope of Complementarity to accommodate National-International Joint Criminal Prosecution for a more functional and effective criminal justice administration in prosecuting international crimes. The result will be of much global interest.

Keywords: Expansion, Scope, Complementarity, International Criminal Law

1. INTRODUCTION

The International Criminal Court² was created to break the vicious cycle of crimes, impunity and conflict. It was set up to contribute to justice, prevention of crimes, peace and security and to guarantee lasting respect for human right and the enforcement of international justice. With the approval of the Rome Statute on the evening of 17 July 1998, it was believed that the mere existence of such a court would help end impunity for major crimes against international law, and would act as a permanent deterrent to despots and tyrants.³ However, unlike the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia (ICTY) and International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR), the ICC does not have primary jurisdiction over national authorities but plays mainly a subsidiary role and supplements domestic courts in the investigation and prosecution of international crimes under article 5 of the Rome Statute. The court is only meant to act when domestic authorities fail to take the necessary step in the investigation and prosecution of international crimes. This is the summary effect of the principle of complementarity. Yet the main challenge is in a situation where a domestic court will show willingness to prosecute an international crime and indeed prosecuted the case but ended in a miscarriage of justice. In such a situation will the ICC have the power to review the case and deliver justice or sit down like a defeated watch dog to allow justice to be miscarried? If the ICC has no jurisdiction to review a case completed by a national court but affected with miscarriage of justice then there is need to make room for joint prosecution of international crimes where a domestic court has shown willingness to prosecute. This

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² The only international criminal court for the prosecution of International crimes specified under Article 5 of the Rome Statute. The Statute came into force on 1 July 2002. (herein after the ICC).

³ AJ Dickerson, (2007) 'Who's in Charge Here? International Criminal Court Complementarity and the Commander's Role in the Courts-Martial', 54 *NAVAL Law Review* (2007) 141, 141.

principle of complementarity was the cornerstone for the acceptance of the Rome statute by state parties and which States parties describe as very essential.⁴ This key concept of the ICC permeates the entire structure and functioning of the international criminal court starting from the very onset of initiating criminal investigation. In effect despite some benefits, the principle of complementarity has in a way caged the ICC in as a dormant watch dog waiting to receive command from the master and where the command fails to come, human right violation can go on. That being said, it is completely unrealistic for the ICC to achieve the desired goal of prompt response to human right violation in the face of this principle of complementarity. There are doubts whether the ICC can actually help to combat impunity and deter future human rights atrocities across the globe. Furthermore, it is estimated to have the resources and capacity to handle only two or three trials a year and the handful of cases pending in its docket will take years to conclude.⁵ More so, as a treaty-based international organization, it only enjoys jurisdiction to hear cases committed in the territory of States Parties, or those referred by the Security Council through its exceptional Chapter VII power in situations that threaten international peace and security.⁶ Finally, the Prosecutor can only focus on criminal acts that occurred after the Rome Statute entered into force in 2002. In effect, these restrictions mean that depending on the ICC to bring many of the world's most serious offenders to justice would be like giving some credit to impunity. This research suggests proactive complementarity of a kind where the ICC will be allowed to engage more actively in a supervisory and monitor-like function with States Parties as well as undertaking criminal investigations, prosecution even providing outreach, technical assistance, and guidance with national courts together and become less passive.⁷ It is in this way that the ICC will be encouraging nations to harmonize their national criminal justice system to assure strong and effective national criminal trials of international crime and think less of the cost of ICC's involvement. This article is divided into three parts. Part I introduced the work and discussed the evolution, concept, nature and the rationale of Complementarity. Part II examined the possibility of expanding the scope of Complementarity. Part III is on recommendations and conclusion.

2. THE EVOLUTION, CONCEPT, NATURE AND THE RATIONALE OF COMPLEMENTARITY

(a) The Evolution and Concept of Complementarity

Complementarity is a fundamental principle upon which the International Criminal Court (ICC) is premised. As a concept it was born out of the negotiation meetings of the UN Ad Hoc Committee of 1994 for the establishment of the International Criminal Court. Amidst discussions and arguments on the draft statute the committee came up with the new concept known as "complementarity" aside the provisions of the draft statute.⁸ It is a principle that governs the relationship between the ICC and national legal orders. The principle of complementarity presents the idea that states, rather than the International Criminal Court will have priority in proceeding with cases within their jurisdiction. It means that the Court will complement, but not supersede, national jurisdiction. National courts will continue to have priority in investigating and prosecuting crimes committed within their jurisdictions, but the International Criminal Court will act when national courts are 'unable or unwilling' to perform their tasks.⁹

⁴ LJ Laplante, (2010) 'The Domestication of International Criminal Law: A Proposal for Expanding the International Criminal Court's Sphere of Influence, 43 J. Marshall L Rev ,635 (2010)' *John Marshal Law Review*, vol 43 640.

⁵ William W. Burke-White, (2008) 'Proactive Complementarity: The International Criminal Court and National Courts in the Rome System of International Justice,' volume 49 *Harvard International Law Journal* (2008) 53, 54. In L J Laplante, *ibid*, (n 5) 3.

⁶ The Rome Statute of International Criminal Court Article 13.

⁷ William W. Burke-White, *ibid*. (n 6).

⁸ Report of the Ad Hoc Committee on the Establishment of the International Criminal Court, UN Doc A/50/22. See also W A Schabas, *An Introduction to the International Criminal Courts* 4th ed(Cambridge University Press 2011)17.

⁹ Roy S. Lee, ('2002), Introduction, in the International Criminal Court: The Making of the Rome Statute: Issues, Negotiations, Results' 2nd ed., (*Kluwer Law International* 2002). 27, Mr. Lee is the Director of the Codification Division in the Office of Legal Affairs of the United Nations and also the Secretary of the International Law Commission and of the Sixth Committee of the General Assembly. He was the Secretary of the Preparatory Committee on the Establishment of an International Criminal

Scholars and even the Office of the prosecutor have interpreted the concept of "complementarity" to not only assure sovereign prerogative in prosecuting serious offenders but in view of the fact that the Rome Statute embodies the principle of *erga omnes*, it therefore places a well recognized obligation on all nations to prosecute crimes that violate *jus cogens* norms.¹⁰ This interpretation finds anchor in the principle of complementarity, which sprung from the determination of negotiators of the Rome Statute who sought to guard domestic jurisdiction from international intrusion, but on a detailed scrutiny it came to mean that this sovereign prerogative is in fact a legal duty of sovereignty.¹¹ In effect, the ICC exists as a constant reminder of states' responsibility to combat impunity. In spite of the fact that the term "complementarity" forms a "cornerstone" of the ICC,¹² there is no explicit reference to it or its definition in the articles of the Rome Statute. The statute only emphasizes in the preamble that 'the International Criminal Court established under this Statute shall be complementary to national criminal jurisdiction.'¹³ Scholars have observed that the word complementarity is meaningless in the abstract, and though a simple intellectual concept, it masks the deep philosophical and political difficulties that the International criminal court must overcome if it is ever to become a functioning institution.¹⁴ To address the gap in definition, scholars have made a resort to the traditional treaty interpretation methods and so complementarity was understood with reference to Article 17 of the Rome Statute.¹⁵ Article 17 regulates admissibility within the restrictions of paragraph 10 of the Rome Statute's preamble emphasizing that international jurisdiction shall "complement" national jurisdiction. Article 17 of the Rome Statute allows the ICC to step in and exercise jurisdiction to prosecute international crime where States are unable or unwilling genuinely to investigate or prosecute, without replacing judicial systems that function properly. "Unwillingness" and "inability" are key concepts in the determination of the admissibility of a case before the ICC. A State may be determined to be "unwilling" when it is clearly shielding someone from his or her responsibility for ICC crimes. Also a State may be "unable" when its legal system has collapsed. Where inability or unwillingness to investigate or prosecute is encountered, it may be necessary to shift the balance of advantages and disadvantages for and against prosecution¹⁶ in order to expedite and aid States to fulfill their role under the ICC's complementarity regime. Following the Kampala Review Conference, positive complementarity increased in significance, and capacity building has firmly entered the vocabulary of international criminal lawyers. The ability of States to fulfill this role has significance not only for their sovereign equality in the community of States, but also for the effectiveness of the ICC in fighting impunity and delivering meaningful justice for victims of mass atrocity. In fact the restricted interpretation of the concept of complementarity and its accompanying struggle, points to the fact that most States are consciously jealous about their powers of criminal prosecution as such powers are linked to the very concept of sovereignty.¹⁷ It has been recognised that the legitimate coercive power of State police is best exemplified through criminal prosecutions,¹⁸ and the

Court. Cited in LE Carter, (2010) 'The Principle of Complementarity and the International Criminal court: the role of *ne bis in idem*. Volume 8 Santa Clara International Law Journal (2010) <http://digitalcommons.law.scu.edu/scujil/vol8/iss1/8>, accessed 20 December 2023.

¹⁰ M Cherif Bassiouni, (1996) 'International Crimes: Jus Cogens and Obligatio Erga Omnes', *59 Law & Contemporary Problems*, (1996) 63, 66.

¹¹ J Laplante, *ibid*, (n 5) 4.

¹² Benjamin Perrin, (2006). 'Making Sense of Complementarity: The Relationship Between the International Criminal Court and National Jurisdictions' 18 *SRI LANKA Journal of International Law* (2006). 301

¹³ Paragraph 10 of the Preamble.

¹⁴ J Laplante, *ibid*, (n 5) 10.

¹⁵ *Ibid*.

¹⁶ See also: O Bekou, 'Complementarity Principle'. [http://www. Oxfordbibliographies.com](http://www.Oxfordbibliographies.com) accessed 20 December 2017.

¹⁷ M M. El Zeidy, (2001) 'The Principle of Complementarity: A New Machinery to Implement International Criminal Law,' 23 *MICH. J. INT'L L.* (2001) 869, 878.

¹⁸ Thomas Hobbes, *The Leviathan* (1660). For discussion of the restrictive approach see generally Immi Tallgren, *Completing the "International Criminal Order" The Rhetoric of International Repression and the Notion of Complementarity in the Draft Statute for an International Criminal Court*, 67 *Nordic Journal of International Law* (1998) 107, 108 128. Cited in J Laplante, *ibid*, (n 5) 10.

exercise of criminal jurisdiction can be said to be a central aspect of sovereignty itself.¹⁹ By virtue of the principle of complementarity as it is in the preamble of the Statute, the court is meant to “supplement” and not “supplant” domestic enforcement of international norms and it is only in extreme cases that the international community should intervene. Thus, under normal circumstance there should be no reason to intervene and no reason for international tribunals.²⁰ According to Newton²¹ the ICC is not after prosecution. Article 17 of the ICC therefore limits the Court’s interventions to only those cases where a State is ‘unable or unwilling’ to prosecute. It speaks to the fact that the ICC is supposed to support domestic proceedings, not circumvent them even as it relates to international crimes. Thus, the key aspect of complementarity is that the ICC is not supposed to overshadow or replace national judicial systems.²² In fact, an ICC intervention should be viewed as a ‘last resort’, only stepping in, in exceptional circumstances. The exceptional circumstances are as specified i.e. where a State is ‘unable or unwilling’ to prosecute individuals suspected of committing international crimes. In the 2009 Prosecutorial Strategy,²³ the ICC defined the principle of complementarity as having two dimensions - one related to the admissibility test in the Rome Statute, and the second as the concept of ‘Positive Complementarity.’ It is the idea that the work of the ICC is not only to allow a State for the first chance to attempt to prosecute a suspect, but that the ICC’s role is to actively bolster the ability of the State to do so which is positive complementarity.” To that extent, Positive complementarity is a “proactive policy of cooperation aimed at promoting national proceedings.

(b)The Nature and Rationale of Complementarity as a Principle in International Criminal Law

The question of complementarity seems to be defined in the statute under article 17 in relation to admissibility of a case rather than the jurisdiction of the court. Though both admissibility and complementarity are issues of competence they are distinguishable, and though closely related they are not the same. The court cannot exercise its jurisdiction under the statute if a case is inadmissible, thus, the principle of complementarity does not affect the existence of jurisdiction of the court strictly speaking but regulates when this jurisdiction may be exercised by the court.²⁴ Article 17 therefore functions as a barrier to the exercise of jurisdiction or as a regulator of the exercise of jurisdiction of the court. In recognition of this fact, the Rules of Procedure and Evidence of the ICC provides that the court shall rule on any challenge to its jurisdiction first before dealing with matters of admissibility.²⁵ Owing to the interpretation section of the Vienna Convention on the interpretation of Treaty, the provisions of a Treaty shall be interpreted, *inter alia* with regard to its object and purpose.²⁶ Obviously the rationale behind the

¹⁹ Ian Brownlie,(1998) *Principles of Public International Law* 5th ed (Oxford University Press 1998) (1966) 289, 303.

²⁰ M A Newton, (2001) ‘Comparative Complementarity: Domestic Jurisdiction Consistent with the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court’, 167 *MIL L REV* (2001) 20, 23.

²¹ Markus Benzing, (2003) ‘The Complementarity Regime of the International Criminal Court: International Criminal Justice between State Sovereignty and the Fight against Impunity’ *Max Planck Yearbook of United Nations Law*, volume 7 (2003) 591-632.

²² Joshua Lam, Contrasting Complementarity: Assessing International Criminal Court’s Support for Domestic Prosecution, in *International Criminal Justice : The ICC and Complementarity International Commission of Jurist, Kenyan Section Journal* ,<http://www.icj-Kenya.org> accessed 28 December 2023.

²³ The Office of the Prosecutor’s Policy Paper on Complementarity coined the term ‘positive complementarity’ in its Prosecutorial Strategy of 2009. In defining how the ICC is a ‘complementary’ court, the OTP policy paper states that one measure of success, regarding the effectiveness of the ICC , is “the absence of trials, as a consequence of the effective functioning of national systems.

²⁴ See also:J Crawford, (2003) ‘The Drafting of the Rome Statute’ In Markus Benzing, ‘The Complementarity Regime of the International Criminal Court: International Criminal Justice between State Sovereignty and the Fight against Impunity’ *Max Planck Yearbook of United Nations Law*, volume 7 (2003) 591-632.

²⁵ Rule 58(4). “The court shall rule on any challenge or question of jurisdiction first and then on any challenge or question of admissibility.”

²⁶ Article 31 of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties valid under Customary International Law.

principle of complementarity is to protect sovereignty²⁷ in general both of State parties and non State parties.

Generally, under international law States have right to exercise criminal jurisdiction over acts within their jurisdiction. It is on this premise that this research is emboldened to submit that exercise of criminal jurisdiction can be said to be a central aspect of sovereignty itself. Quite different from the right of States to exercise criminal jurisdiction over crimes contained in the Statute, the Preamble to the Rome Statute refers to the duty of *every State* not just State parties to exercise its criminal jurisdiction over those responsible for international crimes. Therefore, , another purpose of the complementarity principle could as well be to ensure that States abide by that duty, either by prosecuting the alleged perpetrators themselves or by providing for an international prosecution where they fail to do so. Irrespective of the Rome Statute, States already have the duty to prosecute perpetrators of international crime and which duty precedes the coming into force of the Rome Statute. However, while that duty exists it did not cover all crimes in their different facets under the statutes. It is submitted that the preamble meant crimes within the jurisdiction of the International Criminal Court.²⁸ International crimes may refer to those crimes for which a duty to prosecute exists under other instruments in international law. It is clear that this principle of complementarity was designed to allow for the prosecution of such crimes at the international level where national systems are not doing what is necessary to avoid impunity and deter a future commission of crimes.

Furthermore, apart from the duty to prosecute, the complementarity principle is certainly designed to encourage States to exercise their jurisdiction and make the system of international criminal law enforcement more effective.²⁹ However, the concept of sovereignty is an interest fighting with the interest of the international community in various ways namely in the effective prosecution of international crimes; the endeavour to put an end to impunity, and deterrence of the future commission of such crimes, just to mention a few. There is therefore need to strike a balance between this interest of the international community and State sovereignty.

Another possible rationale which is arguable is that the ICC could be said to be an institution entrusted with the protection of human rights of the accused and victims of international crimes in the national enforcement of international criminal justice.³⁰ Article 17 stipulates that in determining whether a State is unwilling to prosecute, the court shall have regard to the principle of due process recognised by law. The challenge here is whether the court can in theory declare a case inadmissible if a State fervently and over zealously prosecutes war criminals with blatant disregard for the accused person's right to fair trial. If the court can so act it means that the principle of complementarity grants the court the power to review a case where due process was not recognised and which eventually led to miscarriage of justice. This could further be said that with the principle of complementarity the court is enabled not only to intervene in cases of inaction of a State but also in situations where such action leads to breaches of human rights of the accused.³¹ The court is therefore a protector of fair trial standard whether in situations of lack of action or absence of good faith in national procedure, or instances where procedures did not guarantee full respect for the rights of the accused or could not be considered sufficiently impartial. In other words it is

²⁷ M Bergsmo, (2000) 'Occasional Remarks on certain State Concern about the Jurisdictional Research of the International Criminal Court , and their Possible Implications for the Relationship between the Court and the Security Council' *Nord. Journal of International Law* 69 (2000) 87; O Solera, 'Complementary Jurisdiction and International Criminal Justice,' *Int'l Review of the Red Cross* 84 (2002) 145. In M Benzing, *ibid* (n25).

²⁸ Articles 14,15,& 53 of the Statute.

²⁹ P Kirsch, (2002) 'La Cour penale internationale face a la Souverainete des Etats' in A Cassese & M Delmas-Marty, *Crimes Internationaux et Jurisdictions internationales* (2002)31, in M Benzing, *ibid* (n25).

³⁰ Article 17 on issues of admissibility, article 19 On challenges to the jurisdiction of the court or the admissibility of a case.,article 66 on the rights of the accused and article 68 on the protection of the victims and witnesses and their participation in the proceedings.

³¹ M Benzing, *ibid* (n25).

protecting the accused from victor's justice and granting the court the right to reconsider the case.³² Though the court was not created as a human right court strictly speaking but invariably it could be said to be a human right court. This is because one of the reasons for its creation is to address issues which culminate in gross human right violation,³³ to prosecute perpetrators of crimes which violate human rights.

There is yet another possible rationale behind the principle of complementarity. It could be the protection of the right of an accused to be prosecuted by domestic authorities and tried before a domestic court³⁴ unless those authorities or courts are unable or unwilling to do so. This research is emboldened to so submit by the provisions of article 19(2) (a) (b) (c) of the statute which makes it possible for both the State and the accused to challenge the admissibility of a case. A reference has to be made to the fact that the Court's scope of action could be limited for reasons of resource constraints. Thus, in the fight against impunity, the ICC will in addition to serving as a court of last resort where justice cannot be achieved on the national level, but also show case that complementarity principle recognises the fact that national authorities are closer to evidence. It will further ensure that the crimes under jurisdiction of the Court are normally best prosecuted in the State where they have been committed.³⁵ This is because apart from the politics of protecting sovereignty, there is a recognised principle that trials closer to the scene of events at issues have inherent practical and expressive value.

A detailed study into the nature of the principle of Complementarity reveals that complementarity is daisy. While it could be said that it was primarily designed to strike a delicate balance between State sovereignty to exercise jurisdiction and that for effective prevention of such crimes and impunity, the international community has to step in to ensure that its aims and objectives are credibly achieved. At the same time the principle of Complementarity is an implicit restriction of State sovereignty not because it establishes a duty to prosecute, but because it takes away the possibility for States parties and the non territorial sovereign³⁶ to remain inactive in the face of a breach of international law in cases where a duty to prosecute exists under other international instruments.³⁷ The principle of complementarity could also be seen as a cleaver means to stealthily shield and protect a sovereign or make the prosecution of sovereigns an uphill task even in the face of gross human right violations. However complementarity can be effectively waived. From Article 13 of the Rome Statute, the Office of the Prosecutor(OTP) is able to investigate cases that are brought forward in one of three ways:

1. Referral by a State Party
2. Referral by the UNSC (via the authority of a Chapter 7 resolution)
3. Through the *Proprio Motu* powers of the OTP. That is, under the initiative of the Prosecutor, on the basis of complaints that the OTP receives

Situation referrals are key aspects of the work of the ICC, for various reasons. The *pro prio motu* power of the OTP grants the Prosecutor an enormous amount of power, giving the ability to look into possible crimes and situations in any country that is a State Party to the Rome Statute. This power is only limited by the rule that, for any situation that the Prosecutor wishes to investigate more formally,³⁸ she must first obtain approval before ICC judges in chambers. The other two forms of approval do not require chambers

³² DD N Nsereko, (1999) 'The International Criminal Court: Jurisdictional and Related Issue' Criminal Law Forum 10 (1999)87; *ICTY, Prosecutor v Tadic*, Decision on the Defence Motion for Interlocutory Appeal on Jurisdiction, 2 October 1995.

³³ The crime of genocide, crimes against humanity go to the root of human right not excluding war crimes and aggression.

³⁴ The ICTY Appeal Chambers operating in the context of primacy, rather than complementarity in *Prosecutor v Tadic* in the interlocutory appeal on jurisdiction rejected the appellant's argument that he had an exclusive right to be tried by national courts under national laws. Given that the ICTY's statutory framework granted the same fair trial rights to the accused as national courts, the transfer of jurisdiction to an international tribunal did not infringe any rights of the accused.

³⁵ J E Alvarez, (2003), 'The New Dispute Settlers Half) Truth and Consequences,' *Tex. International Law Journal* 39(2003-2004), 405 in M Benzing, *ibid* (n25) 9.

³⁶ In this research the non territorial sovereign is the UN General Assembly.

³⁷ M Benzing, *ibid* (n25) 10..

³⁸ With a view to issuing warrants and starting cases.

approval. The situations that have been initiated using the OTP *proprio motu* power are in Kenya and Côte d'Ivoire.

The Second mechanism is referral by the United Nations Security Council.³⁹ This carries a much broader scope than the other referral mechanisms. UNSC referrals can be directed at any country, including countries that are not State Parties to the Rome Statute. This was the method used to refer the situations in the Sudan and Libya to the ICC. Neither country is a State Party to the Rome Statute, and none of the alleged crimes were committed by nationals of a State Party. It has been argued that the referral of Sudan and Libya by the UNSC, and the subsequent investigations launched by the ICC, are the main reasons for the ongoing debates about the impartiality of ICC interventions.⁴⁰

The third mechanism is the state referral, where a State Party refers its own situation to the ICC and effectively 'waives' complementarity. This has occurred in the Democratic Republic of Congo,⁴¹ Uganda, Central African Republic⁴² and Mali. It has been demonstrated, though, that in order for a State to refer itself to the ICC, it must be a State Party, or must 'acquiesce' to the jurisdiction of the Court, as happened with the Côte d'Ivoire. Furthermore, accepting the jurisdiction of the ICC requires accepting the party to actually be a State, as was shown in the situation where Palestine attempted to submit to the jurisdiction of the ICC,⁴³ but was deferred, due to the fact that Palestine was then not a recognized State.

3. SCOPE OF THE PRINCIPLE OF COMPLEMENTARITY AND THE NEED FOR EXPANSION

The complementarity regime of International Criminal Court serves as a mechanism to encourage and facilitate the compliance of States with their primary responsibility to investigate and prosecute core crimes. Where States fail to genuinely carry out proceedings, the Prosecutor must be ready to move decisively with ICC proceedings. The complementarity regime subsumes the implicit tension of two seemingly contrasting notions in international law namely State sovereignty,⁴⁴ and the international duty to end impunity for international crimes. The complementarity mechanism came as a compromise between those two notions.⁴⁵ Therefore, the Statute recognizes the primary responsibility of States to prosecute international crimes;⁴⁶ and the ICC may only exercise jurisdiction when national legal systems fail to do so, including cases where they are inactive, unwilling or unable genuinely to carry out proceedings. The principle of complementarity is based on two basic pillars: the respect for the primary jurisdiction of States, and considerations of efficiency and effectiveness.⁴⁷ This is a reflection of states generally having the best access to evidence and witnesses, along with the resources to carry out proceedings.

The Office of the Prosecutor, in September 2006, publicized its Prosecutorial Strategy where it declared to have 'adopted a positive approach to complementarity, meaning that it encourages national proceedings where possible; relies on national and international networks; and participates in a system of

³⁹ UNSC.

⁴⁰ Joshua Lam, *ibid* (26)12.

⁴¹ DRC.

⁴² CAR.

⁴³ See also the OTP Statement on Palestine 2012. In November 2012, Palestine was voted into the UN General Assembly as a non-member observer state (see the BBC News report 'Palestinians win upgraded UN Status by Large Margin', 30 November 2012). This may have implications for Palestine's application lodged with the ICC, although this process has, as yet, not moved forward. The OTP has stated that it is still leaving open the possibility of investigations, however, the Assembly of State Parties to the ICC will have to rule on whether they accept Palestine as a state, over and above what was done by the UN General Assembly.

⁴⁴ The primary jurisdiction of States.

⁴⁵ Jann K. Kleffner, (2008) 'Complementarity in the Rome Statute and National Criminal Jurisdictions' (Oxford University Press, 2008) at 3

⁴⁶ Preamble paragraphs 6, Statute of the International Criminal Court, U.N. Doc. A/CONF.183/9.,

⁴⁷ Nidal Nabil Jurd, *The Complementarity Regime of the International Criminal Court in Practice: Is it Truly Serving the Purpose? Some Lessons from Libya*, <https://hr.un.org/sites/hr.un.org/files/The%20Complementarity%20RegimeInternational%20Criminal%20Court>. accessed 22/1/2024.

international cooperation.⁴⁸ In fact, the Office of the Prosecutor began to apply a new test for measuring its success. Accordingly, it explained that its success would not be based on how many cases that reach the ICC but on the contrary, that the absence of trials before this Court, as a consequence of the regular functioning of national institutions, would be a major success.

Though this approach not only reflected a practical and sensible assessment of the ICC's appropriate role, but it also opened the door for more progressive proposals for what this role might look like. In some respects, there is a shift in vision and this shift in the vision of the ICC's appropriate role reflects the fallacy of earlier beliefs that 'the mere existence of the ICC may do much to encourage genuine national proceedings,' with the threat that mere intervention is enough to motivate State action.⁴⁹ History has made such assumption fallacious. Instead, it has become more apparent that the ICC, and in particular the Office of the Prosecutor might need to use more better expansion strategy that could range from diplomatic communications with governments to the provision of assistance in undertaking prosecutions.⁵⁰ The above strategy rather makes the ICC a toothless bulldog that bites no one and the effect can be disastrous. There is need to expand the scope of complementarity for a wider effectiveness. The restriction on ICC not to take up criminal investigation and prosecution of international crimes unless a domestic court has shown that it is unable or unwilling to prosecute, may not help to check impunity.⁵¹ More so, there is no time frame within which the ICC can wait and watch a domestic court to initiate criminal proceeding for the prosecution of a particular crime so as to ascertain its inability or unwillingness to prosecute the crime.

Furthermore, where a State party initiates criminal investigation which is a signal that it is willing to prosecute but unduly delays investigation and/or prosecution, purposely to shield perpetrators, when can the ICC come in to take up the prosecution so as not to breach the principle of complementarity? A widening of the concept of proactive complementarity to include engagement with States Parties, even if it involves matters that technically fall outside the jurisdiction *ratione temporis* found in the Rome Statute's Article 11 and admissibility requirements of Article 17 will go a long way to establish the court's effectiveness. As Burke⁵² suggested, the failure of the court to consciously use its power to catalyze national prosecutions is a potentially dangerous mistake. Furthermore, neglecting the ICC's political and legal power to encourage national prosecutions of international crimes may well undermine the institution's best hope to meet expectations and enhance accountability.⁵³ To avoid either a real or perceived failure, new strategies must be developed to end impunity and to contribute to at least some of the broader expectations of the Court. Such strategies must fit within the ICC's legal, political, and financial limitations. Likewise, such an approach would help further the Court's other goals, such as national reconciliation and judicial reconstruction. There is need for a national-international joint criminal prosecution.

4. NATIONAL-INTERNATIONAL JOINT CRIMINAL PROSECUTION

The preamble to the Rome Statute affirms and recognizes national-international criminal prosecution when it states that 'the most serious crimes of concern to the international community as a whole must not go unpunished. It further states that their effective prosecution must be ensured by taking measures at the national level and by enhancing international cooperation.' Put in lofty terms, the Rome Statute reflects the notion that the sovereign nations of the world are joined, not as competitors in the pursuit of sovereign

⁴⁸ See also: Jessica 'Almqvist, (2008) 'Complementarity and Human Rights: A Litmus Test for the International Criminal Court', 30 *LOY. L.A. International & Comparative Law Review* (2008) 335, 354 (citing Philippe Kirsch, Address to the U.N. General Assembly, U.N. Doc. 3 (Nov. 1, 2007). In J Laplante, *ibid*, (n 5) 10.

⁴⁹ William W. Burke-White, (2008) 'Proactive Complementarity: The International Criminal Court and National Courts in the Rome System of International Justice,' 49 *Harvard International Law Journal* (2008). 53, 54

⁵⁰ *Ibid*.

⁵¹ Note that the state party not have any provision for such crimes in its national laws irrespective of ratification.

⁵² *Supra* .

⁵³ William W. Burke-White, *ibid* (n 42) 14-15.

self interest, but as interdependent components of a larger global civil society in the fight against impunity.⁵⁴ By extension it could be suggestive of joint criminal prosecution for global interest. The ICC can intervene and assist national courts at times in prosecuting international crimes. This intervention may include interaction between ICC judges and National court judges adjudicating over a matter to complement the other, training of officials, the provision of resources, or assistance with investigations or even in a joint criminal prosecution comprising of national and ICC judges. The Rome Statute therefore is expected to do more than simply define the limits of the Court's power. The statute should instead re-affirm its role as a catalyst to help States fulfill their pre-existing treaty obligations which is the duty of prosecuting international crimes. In this way, complementarity principle is only minted to build on the well-established pre-existing practice of nations in enforcing international law.

In effect, the Rome Statute only reinforces a central role of national criminal justice institutions in that it does not merely reiterate a general competence of States to exercise criminal jurisdiction over such crimes, but stipulates that it is a binding duty on States to do so. In international law it is a duty on States to enforce international criminal law. The preamble to the Rome Statute is only reminding and re-affirming that it is the duty of every State to exercise its criminal jurisdiction over those responsible for international crimes. Thus, the Preamble's declaration indicates that the duty to prosecute precedes the coming into force of the Rome Statute since it arises out of treaty and customary law. It is a duty that has been there though what is meant by international crimes in the Rome Statute only came to be known as international crimes with the coming into force of the Rome Statute. By this reasoning complementarity will no longer mean that sovereigns have a discretionary prerogative to prosecution, but rather "an implicit restriction" on their State sovereignty to prosecute. There will be no more possibility for State parties to remain inactive, even under a breach of international law in cases where a duty to prosecute exists under other instruments. The principle thus, gives effect to, and indeed completes the idea of an effective decentralized prosecution of international crimes.⁵⁵ Where this decentralized prosecution of international crimes is not forthcoming the Rome Statute should expand the scope of complementarity to accommodate situations where the ICC could join force with national courts to ensure that perpetrators of international crimes are prosecuted. This reasoning is based on the premise that international crimes are offenses against the law of nations, and by their very nature affect the world community as a whole. Thus, all States and States institutions carry the international obligation that places an affirmative duty on them to either extradite or prosecute alleged violators of international crimes.⁵⁶ In the end, it is in the interest of the international community in the effective prosecution of international crimes, the endeavor to put an end to impunity, and the deterrence of the future commission of such crimes.

Nonetheless, despite the fact that the duty to prosecute belongs to all States, and thus all States Parties to the Rome Statute, any positive involvement of the ICC would only occur with regard to situations that would potentially fall within the ICC's *ratione temporis* jurisdiction set in Article 11. Yet the ICC's focus on only those States Parties falling within the strict temporal limits of the Rome Statute runs contrary to the overarching aim of the ICC to combat impunity in collaboration with *all* nations. Indeed, the Rome Statute elucidates customary international law that is binding on all States. States acting pursuant to these universal standards will contribute to the development of international criminal law regardless of whether they are members of the ICC or have cases that fall within its jurisdiction. This is a very critical stage in the development of the relationship between the International Criminal Court and National courts and in developing an international-national criminal justice administration within the context of the Rome Statute.

Therefore it may be the right time to re-examine the assumption of jurisdictional limits to the concept of complementarity, with an eye toward expanding the ICC's global influence. The ICC may exert a type of moral persuasion that can aid countries in maintaining the momentum and quality of transitional justice

⁵⁴ See also: M A Newton, *Ibid* (n 24).

⁵⁵ J Laplante, *ibid*, (n 5) 47. See also M Benzing, *ibid* (n25)

⁵⁶ M Cherif Bassiouni, (1999) 'Crimes against Humanity in International Criminal Law 2d ed (Martinus nijhoff ed., 1999) 515.

projects.⁵⁷ In general, the field of transitional justice concerns itself with the mechanisms adopted by governments seeking to address past episodes of political violence, repression, armed conflict, and other situations that give rise to systematic violation of human rights and humanitarian law. Indeed most situations that will trigger the ICC's jurisdiction will also trigger the initiation of transitional justice processes because both are concerned with conflict and post-conflict setting.

It is submitted that where national-international joint criminal prosecution is adopted, the possibility of having law enforcement agents in every nation State will be actualized. The ICC rather than rely on the unwilling State tools⁵⁸ to apprehend indictees can easily work with its own law enforcement agents residing in these States to effect arrests. This will help promote speedy dispensation of justice by the ICC and reduce the long period of time often wasted to effect a single arrest.

5. COMPLEMENTARITY AND THE UNITED NATIONS' SECURITY COUNCIL

The relationship between the Security Council and the ICC in referring a situation to the court, and the application of complementarity regime is not very clear. While article 18⁵⁹ does not apply to Security Council referrals, article 19⁶⁰ does. It has been argued that the complementary regime does not as such apply to such referral.⁶¹ The Security Council in a resolution referring a situation to the court may declare a situation admissible, for example by declaring a State unable or unwilling to investigate or prosecute. This raises the question whether the court would be bound by such a decision. Reference to the ICC intended as an independent and impartial international organisation with the power to determine its own competence, is not sufficient as such.

The independence of the court and its judges only exist within the ambit of the legal frame work established by the Statute and does not actually preclude the influence of other organs or question of jurisdiction and admissibility.⁶² The Statute presupposes that the court will apply the complementarity principle to Security Council referrals too. Article 53(1)(b) requires the prosecutor to have regard to the admissibility of the case when deciding whether to initiate an investigation also if the case has been referred to the court by the Security Council.⁶³ While some argue that the court would not be bound by a determination of admissibility by the Security Council since article 24, 25, 103 of the Charter of the UN only addresses UN Member States not international organisations; others rightly contend that decisions of the Security Council under Chapter VII of the UN Charter are binding on international organisations. This is so at least in as much as they are established by UN Members States since States cannot vest an international organisation with more powers than they themselves have.⁶⁴ States must not circumvent their own duties under the UN Charter by creating an international organisation which exercises its duties in contradiction to the United Nations and its organs. Since the ICC has been created by States as a complementary institution and retained the right to investigate and prosecute international crimes unless deemed unwilling or unable by the court, the Security Council may not ignore that restriction on the court's scope of action.⁶⁵ Accordingly, the persuasive weight of the Security Council has the potency of making it difficult for the court to disagree with a determination by the council. However, the question is, on who lies the burden of proving the unwillingness or inability of a State to genuinely investigate or

⁵⁷ Christine H. Chung, (2007) 'The Punishment and Prevention of Genocide: The International Criminal Court as a Benchmark of Progress and Need', 40 *CASE W. RES. J. INT'L L.* (2007) 227, 241. See also J Laplante, *ibid.*, (n 5) 47.

⁵⁸ States law enforcement agents whose master could be an indictee and who are bound to obey their master.

⁵⁹ On Preliminary rulings regarding admissibility.

⁶⁰ On the Challenges to the jurisdiction of the Court or the admissibility of a case

⁶¹ Though some scholars like Cassese, and Holmes have a different view. See M Benzing, *ibid* (n25) R Dixon/ K AA Khan/ R May, eds, Archibold, International Criminal Courts, Practice, Procedure and Evidence (2003)1182.

⁶² J Laplante, *ibid.*, (n 5) 36.

⁶³ P Gargiulo, 'The Controversial Relationship Between the International Criminal Court and the Security Council,' in M Benzing, *ibid* (n25) 36.

⁶⁴ See also: E de Wet, (2000) 'Judicial Review as an Emerging General Principle of Law and its Implication for the International Court of Justice' 47 *NILR* (2000) 181.

⁶⁵ J Laplante, *ibid.*, (n 5) 36.

prosecute a crime. The law is that he who asserts must prove so the burden is very likely to rest on the prosecutor just as the burden of proving the guilt of an accused rests on the prosecution, but unfortunately in this case, it is on the State. By the principle of complementarity there could be said to be a consensual division of labour between the State and the Court yet, the State may possibly waive its right to investigate and claim complementarity as a bar to admissibility. One of the possible grounds for such a waiver could spring up where the case is of international importance and/or politically too sensitive for the State to handle it itself.

As Benzings, rightly argued, if the complementary principle is read as a safeguard of national sovereignty in the form of the right to prosecute, then it is indeed convincing to argue that a state by declining to exercise the right, under general international law, may waive its primacy and so enable the court to act.⁶⁶ If on the other hand the complementarity principle did not exclusively protect State sovereignty, but also created a right for the individual,⁶⁷ then such a waiver by a State would not be possible. This is because the State cannot unilaterally take away a right of a person that it has agreed to in a multilateral instrument.⁶⁸ However, there is no such right for the individual in the statute. Therefore handing over the prosecution to the international plane would not amount to a breach of an international obligation since the State concerned would fulfill its obligation by ensuring that the court investigates and adjudicates the crimes, provided that the court actually initiates proceedings. Without honest co-operation from the State and the Security Council the success of the court in addressing issues of impunity will end in a deadlock. A solution will be a resort to proactive complementarity and expand the scope to adopt a joint International-national criminal prosecution, otherwise the principle is already an excessive concession to State sovereignty, potentially endangering the success of the endeavour to establish the first permanent international institution with jurisdiction over the most serious international crimes.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

In the light of the above discussions and findings, the article recommends that the ICC should be given primacy over national courts once the crimes involved are international crimes within the jurisdiction of the ICC just like the ICTY and ICTR if the world community is serious with checking impunity. There should be a national-international joint criminal prosecution of international crimes. Indeed, the use of ordinary crimes to define international crimes within national jurisdictions may well be the hidden weakness in the complementarity regime as an effective limit to supranational power. In line this, domestic courts to arrange their domestic substantive laws to reflect and include the range of offenses under the Rome Statue for effective prosecution since you cannot put something on nothing and expect it to stand. The mere existence of the legislative framework is fundamental because there can be no utilisation of that framework in circumstances where it does not exist. There has to be in each state that is a UN member an office of international criminal court police force to assist the ICC in effecting arrests.

In conclusion, the reality which is a very hard truth is that while a ‘zero case’ scenario is a worthwhile aim, cases have found their ways to the ICC in The Hague. This is in the first place the result of the contradiction that the Court will have jurisdiction only when a State party is unwilling or unable to do the job itself. Obviously if “complementarity principle” had existed in the London agreement, “Nuremberg Tribunal” wouldn’t have been such a memorable history today. By virtue of the principle of complementarity, the court is meant to “supplement” and not “supplant” domestic enforcement of international criminal norms and it is only in extreme cases that the international criminal court should intervene. Therefore, under normal circumstance there should be no reason to intervene and no reason for international tribunals. In fact the ICC is not after prosecution, then why create a court at all? Limiting the Court’s interventions to only those cases where a State is ‘unable or unwilling’ to prosecute, and placing the court as a court of ‘last resort’, in cases of international crimes is simply according

⁶⁶ *Ibid.*

⁶⁷ Rome Statute Article 19 (2)(a).

⁶⁸ J Laplante, *ibid.*, (n 5) 40.

impunity a soft landing. History has proved it right. Furthermore, where a State is unwilling or unable to prosecute, and ICC takes over, in terms of arrest, the ICC prosecutor is a stateless actor, with no international police force to assist him in effecting arrests. He is at the mercy, if you like, of the State that is implicated in the international crimes he wishes to investigate. To get his hands on an accused he needs the same State to be his eyes and ears on ground and to arrest when possible. How can a State that is unable or unwilling to prosecute a crime effectively assist in arrest. Of course it will never work otherwise Al Bashir of Sudan wouldn't have been an issue. In fact, a detailed analysis of the principle will reveal that complementarity has the potential to signal the beginning of the end of the ICC. By that principle the Rome Statute itself contemplates an institution that may never be employed, and that is if domestic courts will perform their duties of prosecuting these international crimes. But the question is how can a domestic court prosecute a crime that is not part of its substantive national law? What happens where the person to be prosecuted is the very person in power and/or behind the atrocity that occurred? The ICC is one component of a regime consisting of a network of States that have undertaken to do the ICC's work for it even when they are not serious to do the work, to act as domestic ICCs in respect of international crimes even when they have not made those crimes part of their laws. How then can such agreement be effective? Primacy has to be given to the ICC over national court with respect to international crimes. While this is contemplated the weight of the Security Council on the court has to be checked. This is because the persuasive weight of the Security Council has the potency of making it difficult for the court to disagree with a determination by the council.